

PLAN-B

Tackling light and noise pollution

Recommendations for Large-Scale Monitoring of Artificial Light Emissions at Night

(D2.1 Light Pollution Mapping with Underpinning Methodology)

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 Recommendations for Large-Scale Monitoring of Artificial Light Emissions at Night

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List of Acronyms

ALAN	Artificial Light At Night
AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
CBAS	International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals
CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CCT	Correlated Color Temperature
DN	Digital Number
DMSP-OLS	Defense Meteorological Satellite Program - Operational Linescan System
IAA-CSIC	Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain)
ISS	International Space Station
JL1/JB-3	Jilin-1 satellite constellation
LDT	Luminaire Data Table
MODTRAN	Moderate Resolution Atmospheric Transmission
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NTL	Night-Time Light
PAN	Panchromatic
PSF	Point Spread Function
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (Germany)
REECL	Red Española de Estudios de Contaminación Lumínica
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
SAND	Spectrophotometer for Aerosol Night Detection
SDGSAT-1	Sustainable Development Goals Satellite 1
SQM	Sky Quality Meter
ULOR	Upward Light Output Ratio
UCM	Universidad Complutense de Madrid
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
VIIRS-DNB	Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite - Day/Night Band
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984

Executive summary (publishable)

Artificial light at night (ALAN) has become a widespread pollutant with profound ecological, cultural, and economic consequences. This document outlines a set of science-based recommendations for establishing a harmonized system of large-scale monitoring across Europe and beyond. It identifies three core metrics essential for regulatory and conservation strategies: total light emissions, nocturnal ecological connectivity, and the quality of the nightscape. Drawing on satellite data, ground-based instrumentation, and open-source inventories, the report proposes minimum technical standards for photometers, cameras, and datasets to ensure traceable, reproducible, and policy-relevant measurements. The 2023 Granada Manifesto is presented as a foundational step toward the legal recognition of light as a pollutant under European environmental regulatory framework. The integration of artificial light into environmental monitoring frameworks, particularly the European Environment Monitoring System, is urged to align ALAN governance with biodiversity protection, energy efficiency, and cultural heritage preservation. This framework aims to empower regulators, researchers, and civil society to implement informed, effective, and enforceable mitigation measures.

Related documents

[PLAN-B_D4.1 - Light Pollution Policy Brief](#)

1 Object of the deliverable

This **document** is not intended to be a scientific article, but rather a **compilation of accumulated knowledge**, some of which may or may not have been part of peer-reviewed publications. It is also not intended to be a static document, as the author and their collaborators are actively working -as part of the PLAN-B project and other initiatives to address some of the current limitations.

The **measurement of light pollution**, like any other scientific topic, **is subject to certain constraints**. Nevertheless, the recent surge in light pollution can, in part, be attributed to the lack of proper regulation and the absence of concrete, measurable objectives to guide mitigation efforts[1]. At the November 2023 meeting held in Granada[2], **three indicators were agreed upon to evaluate the success of light pollution control**: the total amount of **luminous emissions**, the existence of **nocturnal biological corridors**, and the **preservation of the nightscape**. These three indicators can be measured with currently available systems; however, systematic assessment is not yet standard practice due to a lack of political will. Still, there are existing legal commitments that require the evaluation of these metrics to assess the achievement of proposed objectives. Throughout this document, we

will detail the resources available at the time of writing. This document will be reviewed at least annually until the conclusion of the PLAN-B project[3].

2 Context and justification

Light pollution poses a **growing threat to biodiversity, human health, night sky quality, and energy efficiency**. Its spread has been rapid and sustained, already affecting **over 99% of the European population**[4] and an **increasing share of protected ecosystems**. The lack of regulatory recognition of artificial nighttime light as a pollutant has hindered the implementation of systematic mitigation measures. Nevertheless, various international frameworks, such as the Declaration in Defense of the Night Sky and the Right to Starlight (2007), UNEP/CMS Resolution 13.5 (2020), the European Green Deal and Nature Restoration Regulation, have already called out its negative impact and the urgent need to address it through appropriate legislation and monitoring. Also, it is clear that the **reduction of light pollution is key to achieving several of the Sustainable Development Goals**[5].

The 2023 Granada Manifesto[2] on light pollution highlights the imperative for the European Union to formally recognize light as a polluting agent and to incorporate its measurement into the European Environment Monitoring System (EEM). It also emphasizes that more than 99% of artificial nighttime light ultimately affects the environment, with enormous energy and ecological costs-estimated at over 38 TWh and €6.3 billion per year in the EU prior to the 2022 energy crisis. Subsequently, it was also supported in the [Light Pollution Policy Brief](#), published by the PLAN-B project in June 2025.

3 Limitations of Traditional Monitoring

Although **light pollution monitoring has traditionally been done at small scales**, by volunteers and not by environmental agencies-with few exceptions like the National Park Services or MeteoGalicia[6], Badajoz, or the Netherlands[7] (not operational now to our knowledge), other scientific networks are broader but not restricted to a specific area, such as the “*Red Española de Estudios de Contaminación Lumínica*”¹, Globe at Night Network² and the North Italy network[8], **as well as intensive single-station measurements**[9]. These efforts have typically used standardised, well-established methods, such as ground-based photometry measuring light levels with luxometers or a few photometers like Sky Quality Meters, and visual observation campaigns, but these

¹ <https://guaix.fis.ucm.es/reecl/>

² <https://globeatnight.org>

methods are insufficient to effectively characterise light pollution at regional, state, or continental scales on their own[10]. This does not mean that these devices are useless; they have been instrumental for much of the research done to date and will continue to be useful in the future[11]. However, we should not expect them to achieve goals they were not designed for, as described in their design documentation[12], [13], without the necessary corrections.

Mapping total emissions and setting limits is essential for effective control of light pollution[4], and this is not possible when relying on microscale assessments and complaint-based controls, which remain common in some countries. Moreover, to effectively comply with the Natura 2000 network regulatory framework, which requires preserving natural conditions as much as possible, it is crucial to monitor both the landscape and the connectivity of these areas to prevent populations from becoming isolated in 'biodiversity islands'[14], [15]. Traditional monitoring typically focuses on legal and lighting standard compliance in populated areas and on the sky brightness levels at the zenith in already dark locations (often for astrotourism). These metrics are clearly insufficient to ensure environmental preservation. On one hand, photometric measurements in urban settings are rarely audited and are typically carried out systematically and centrally only for public lighting.

Another current limitation is the lack of standard or even explicit guidelines for designing light pollution measurement and monitoring systems, despite no technical barriers to doing so. Lack of interest and training can also play a role, as some stakeholders have commented. The market for light pollution measurement devices is simply too small. In practice, there is a convergence of parameters among various photometers, but they still fall short, except in a few cases of meeting the minimum requirements needed for informed decision-making by non-expert public managers and the public.

4 Total Amount of Light Introduced into the Environment

4.1 Introduction

Knowing **the total emissions** of any pollutant is the **first step to understanding and managing its impact** on natural and social systems. This premise is even more **critical** when solid evidence exists of **severe effects on biodiversity**[16]. Without comprehensive quantification, it is impossible to identify trends, assess the effectiveness of mitigation strategies, or establish scientific thresholds and ecological limits to guide regulation and land use planning. In the case of chemical pollutants, e.g. from nitrogen oxides to

microplastics, decades of research have shown that the total magnitude of discharge determines bioaccumulation in the food chain, soil and ocean acidification, aquatic ecosystem eutrophication, and a wide array of sublethal effects ranging from endocrine disruption to community collapse.

Artificial light at night (ALAN) is no exception. Despite lacking tangible mass, its energy interacts with organisms at the molecular, cellular, and behavioural levels, causing disorientation in migratory birds, alteration of circadian rhythms in plants and animals, and dramatic shifts in predator-prey dynamics.

Quantifying total emissions also allows the integration of spatial and temporal dimensions into the analysis. On one hand, it **reveals territorial inequalities:** hyper luminous **urban areas** create “peninsulas” of light pollution that extend for tens of kilometers, **affecting rural areas and nature reserves.** On the other hand, it **provides a historical view** of the issue’s **evolution,** essential for correlating **biodiversity trajectories** with socioeconomic development patterns and public policy implementation (e.g., energy-efficiency standards or regulations requiring controlled-spectrum luminaires). From an **environmental management perspective,** having **global figures facilitates comparisons between regions**[11], prioritises interventions, and **helps allocate resources.** It also underpins national inventories and drives international agreements-much like greenhouse gases with the Kyoto Protocol or persistent organic pollutants with the Stockholm Declaration. Without this quantitative knowledge, strategies rely on conjecture and risk being inefficient or, worse, counterproductive.

Finally, transparency and accountability depend on the objective measurement of total emissions. Civil society, regulatory agencies, and the scientific community need a common language-based on verifiable data-to debate commitments and monitor progress. Thus, quantifying **artificial light emitted into the environment** is not merely an academic exercise: it **is the cornerstone of comprehensive policies** aimed at safeguarding biodiversity, the night sky, and human health.

4.2 Metric importance

The *total amount of light introduced into the environment* stands as a crucial indicator for several complementary reasons:

- **Environmental impact assessment.**

Measuring total luminous flux ($W\ m^{-2}$) allows direct correlation between artificial lighting pressure and observed changes in ecological systems. This quantitative reference helps **identify tolerance thresholds of sensitive species,** quantify darkness loss in priority habitats, and gauge synergistic effects with other stressors (e.g., noise, temperature, or

chemical pollutants). Without it, one cannot distinguish whether detected impacts stem from local lighting design variations or regional light pollution. Regardless of how complicated the light path is[17], all living beings, including humans, are impacted in one way or another by the introduction of ALAN. And that impact comes, in the first order, from the quantity of emissions.

- **Spatial and temporal comparison.**

The metric allows for **comparisons across** neighborhoods, cities, regions, and **countries**, regardless of their size or population density. Annual time series reveal trends: increases associated with urban growth or changes in lighting technologies; stagnations due to economic crises; and declines following the implementation of responsible lighting regulations. These baselines are **essential for assessing the effectiveness of mitigation programs** and for identifying hotspots where intensified efforts are needed.

- **Detection of adverse effects of lighting policies and cultures.**

The **application of different lighting policies**, such as using (or misusing) certain standards instead of the *As Low As Reasonably Achievable (ALARA)* principle[18], or regulations focused solely on electricity use without considering light pollution consequences, **is crucial**[1]. A **reduction in kWh does not** necessarily translate to **less light pollution**. Quantifying emitted light, not just consumed energy, verifies whether LED installations, curfew regulations, or photometric design guidelines truly reduce environmental luminous flux, thereby avoiding the typical “rebound effect”[19], where cheaper, **more efficient lamps are used in greater numbers or for longer durations**. It is also known that there is a cultural component to lighting practices that can lead to higher emissions of ALAN[20].

- **Support for light propagation models and forecasts.**

Radiative models estimating sky brightness or light propagation distance require a reliable input: **total emission from sources**. Calibrated, georeferenced emission data improve simulation accuracy and, consequently, urban planning tools, infrastructure design, and astronomical-protection zone delineation. They also enable scenario generation under various urban growth or corrective-measure assumptions, providing decision-makers with a solid scientific basis for proactive action.

4.3 Technical Requirements

Obtaining the total amount of light introduced into the environment demands a rigorous instrumental and methodological framework. The **minimum requirements for ensuring data comparability and traceability** are detailed below.

4.3.1 Absolute Radiometric Measurements

To be physically meaningful, all **records must be expressed in absolute radiometric units**:

- **Spectral radiance** ($\text{W m}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$): power emitted, reflected, or transmitted per unit apparent area, per unit solid angle, and per unit wavelength.
- **Luminance** (cd m^{-2}): photometric measure weighted by the human eye sensitivity curve, useful for lighting audits and visual comfort standards. However, this alone is insufficient to establish light pollution levels and must be accompanied at least by the source's correlated colour temperature.

Sensors used (photometers, radiometers, calibrated cameras, satellites) shall:

- Be calibrated either by the manufacturer or through intercalibration with other sensors that are themselves calibrated using recognized standards or stable natural references (e.g., photometrically stable stars). These measurements serve as screening data and are not legally binding.
- Where and when possible, ensure **traceable calibration to national or international standards**, such as those provided by the *National Institute of Standards and Technology* (NIST, USA) or the *Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt* (PTB, Germany). Such traceable calibrations are essential for applications in regulatory contexts, where legal enforceability is required, although they may be too demanding for broad-scale monitoring of light pollution.
- Possess a **dynamic range** sufficient to measure from natural background light levels up to the brightest urban illuminance levels.
- Include metadata on **measurement uncertainty** (expressed as a percentage) and provide the **full spectral response curves** of the sensor.

It is essential to be aware of each method's limitations and compensate by synergistically combining methods with differing constraints.

4.3.2 Photon Estimation

Photon counting enables analysis of light as a quantum flux, crucial for chronobiology and photochemistry studies.

- Convert radiance L_λ to **radiance in photon units** Q_λ via: $Q_\lambda = \frac{L_\lambda \lambda}{h c}$, where h is Planck's constant, and c is the speed of light.
- Perform calculations by Red, Green and Blue (**RGB bands**) or, ideally, in 10–20 nm segments to capture sensitivity differences in nocturnal taxa (insects, bats, seabirds).

- **Temporal resolution:** record the exact time of satellite overpasses, as light emissions vary throughout the night.

4.3.3 Recommended Corrections

In most cases, the data is not immediately ready for use. In this section, we mention the corrections that should ideally be performed. This does not mean that the values are not useful as presented, but authors must be aware that **failing to apply these corrections may significantly increase measurement error**. Currently, uncertainty in light pollution trends is so high that estimated annual growth rates range from 2% [19], [21] to 10% [22].

This is partly **due to methodological and technical limitations** [13], [23]. The precision of measurements should be sufficient to support political decisions that are not misleading. These **corrections are recommended** but not always essential.

- **Atmospheric.** Compensate for Rayleigh and Mie scattering, absorption by water vapor, ozone, and aerosols (particulate matter); apply radiative-transfer models (6S, MODTRAN) and near-real-time aerosol optical depth (AOD) coefficients.
- **Geometric and angular.** Orthorectify imagery, correct for parallax and Earth curvature [24], [25], normalize to nadir or mean observation angle; convert to common cartographic coordinates (WGS84, UTM).
- **Surface reflectance.** Account for ground reflectance effects when estimating true emissions—for example, whether surfaces are typically wet, snowy, or of a particular material type [24], [26].
- **Cloud and high-reflectance masking** (snow, light-colored sands) to avoid false positives.

4.3.4 Cross-Calibration

Sensor heterogeneity requires systematic intercomparison:

1. **Spectral harmonization:** remap bands to a common spectral response via convolution matrices or spectral-unmixing methods.
2. **Spatial adjustment:** degrade or enhance resolution to match the coarsest pixel grid, quantifying variance loss.
3. **Reference sites** (deserts, oceans, portable laboratory sites) [27] visited periodically to verify gain and offset drifts.
4. **In situ validation:** networks of high-sensitivity photometers (Sky Quality Meters, calibrated DSLRs, light meters connected to radiation networks) synchronized with satellite overpasses to close the verification loop.

4.4 Available Measurement Systems

4.4.1 Satellites

Satellite imagery provides the **most robust and accurate method** currently available for **measuring ALAN across spatial and temporal scales**. Unlike ground-based measurements, which are constrained by access, logistics, or sampling bias, satellites offer **consistent and standardised observations** across the entire globe. This universality is particularly crucial for assessing light pollution in remote areas, across national borders, and in regions where local monitoring infrastructure is lacking.

From a methodological standpoint, **modern night-time satellite sensors**, such as the *VIIRS Day/Night Band*, are equipped with **high-bit-depth radiometry and onboard calibration**. These instruments offer traceable and reproducible measurements that meet scientific standards for temporal continuity and radiometric accuracy [28]. Such characteristics make them ideally suited for monitoring trends, evaluating policy interventions, and validating predictive models.

Additionally, the **spatial resolution of current platforms** (e.g., 740 m for VI-IRS, 130 m for Luojia-1, and sub-metric for commercial constellations like Jilin-1) allows researchers to **capture urban lighting structures at the street or district level** while maintaining synoptic perspectives at the national or continental scale [29]. This **multi-scale** capability cannot be matched by fixed photometers, which **only offer point measurements**.

Satellite data are also **freely and systematically available in most cases** (e.g., *VIIRS products VNP46A1-A4 via NASA Earthdata*), enabling cost-effective monitoring without the need for field campaigns, maintenance, or site-specific calibration[30]. Moreover, satellites **observe all sources of light**: public, private, vehicular[24], [31], [32], [33], [34], ornamental, **without dependence on local inventories**, which often omit significant emitters such as commercial facades or domestic lighting[35]. **One limitation of VIIRS** in this regard is the **temporal variability of the sources**, which can currently be **addressed** by using **SDGSAT-1 and ISS data**.

Although directionality and local obstacles are critical for understanding small-scale lighting effects, it is **important** to note that **at broader spatial scales** (even transboundary [36]), much of the **light scattered by the ground and other surfaces** accumulates and contributes to the **diffuse glow** that envelops urban environments. This scattered light becomes **part of the general skyglow** that dominates the nighttime light signature of cities as observed from satellites.

Satellite-detected night-time light (NTL) has consistently proven to be a reliable **proxy** for various socioeconomic indicators, particularly **public lighting expenditure**[37] and overall

electricity consumption[38]. Although it does not resolve fine-scale directional differences, satellite NTL captures the integrated result of both direct emissions and accumulated diffuse light, making it invaluable for large-scale environmental, urban, and policy analyses.

In summary, **satellite imagery provides** a scientifically rigorous, **globally harmonised**, and **scalable solution to assess and manage light pollution**. Ground-based instruments remain valuable for spectral characterisation and fine-scale validation, but it is the objective, cultural-bias-free orbital view that enables coherent regulation and understanding of night-time illumination patterns worldwide. Of course, limitations remain, and signal reduction due to spectral issues must be addressed. For more information, consult [39].

DMSP-OLS The DMSP-OLS series provides the longest **continuous record of nighttime lights** (1992–2013), with daily global coverage and well-established products for “stable lights” and mean radiance composites. However, it **lacks onboard calibration**. Its digital numbers (DN 1–63) require complex intercalibration to compare across years and have a coarse spatial resolution of approximately 3 km[21], [37]. Furthermore, bright urban cores often saturate the sensor, and its narrow spectral response (< 500 nm) limits detection of newer lighting technologies. The acquisitions were mainly made in the early hours.

VIIRS-DNB VIIRS-DNB delivers 14-bit calibrated radiometry without saturation over cities, with substantially improved spatial resolution (740 m) and freely available daily data. Its single panchromatic band (505–890 nm), however, cannot distinguish blue-rich LED emissions[21].

There is also a small level of blurring due to the shape of the satellite’s point spread function (PSF)[40]. Products are available on daily, monthly, and annual bases. The raw data can include up to six images per night. Currently, data are collected by Suomi-NPP, NOAA-20, and NOAA-21. Suomi data are available since 2012, NOAA-20 since 2018, and NOAA-21 is still under commissioning. Acquisitions typically occur between 00:45 and 06:00 local solar time. Calibration differences between products are generally small but can be significant over large areas[41]. VIIRS is an extremely sensitive data source capable of detecting surface albedo in desertic areas, so when analysing large areas, it is important to subtract natural components such as albedo and airglow[42]. The latest Collection 2 of *VNP46A2* from *NASA’s Black Marble team* has been optimised for these purposes.

ISS Astronaut Photography Night-time imagery from the International Space Station (ISS) achieves very high spatial resolution (5–200 m) and true RGB colour[43], with the potential for absolute calibration via standard stars and stabilised mounts[44]. These observations, however, are irregular and unscheduled, resulting in patchy coverage; images may suffer from motion blur and inconsistent radiometric quality. These issues have been partially addressed using time-lapses with wide fields of view. The data have been available since

2003, with most imagery collected from 2010 to the present[20]. Inside PLAN-B, we are working on EU large-scale maps.

Luojia-1 Luojia-1 supplies moderate (130 m) resolution nighttime data with a 15-day revisit cycle and broad panchromatic sensitivity (460–980 nm), all provided free of charge[45]. Its revisit rate is relatively slow for rapid monitoring, and the absence of multispectral bands limits the ability to discriminate among different lighting sources. It was only available during 2019.

SDGSAT-1 SDGSAT-1 is the first global night-time sensor offering both RGB and panchromatic bands from a 505 km orbit, combining fine spectral resolution (10 m PAN and 40 m RGB) with medium sensitivity. As a recently launched platform (2021), its time series is short, and extensive validation is still pending. **The data must be requested but is free of charge for scientific use.** It is a growing resource and, as part of the RALAN-Map, PLAN-B projects and the EU map³ [46], **it will be available for research purposes.**

JL1/JB-3 (Jilin-1) The JL1/JB-3 commercial constellation provides very high spatial resolution (~ 1 m) panchromatic and multispectral imagery on demand, well-suited to detailed urban studies. Coverage is limited by a narrow swath width, and a tasking model-imagery is only acquired upon request. Also, there are no routine global products for continuous monitoring[39]. Its ideal use is to identify individual light sources and light levels that can be directly compared with ground data.

4.4.2 Ground-based Photometry

In general, there are **few photometers** that meet the **technical specifications for general photometric measurements** by non-experts aiming **to control light pollution.**

Both [12] and [13] highlighted the serious limitations of using panchromatic photometers. This was demonstrated experimentally in [9]. Typically, this is not a major issue for photometers installed in intrinsically dark locations, as calculated by [62], but it is critical for monitoring total emissions. Generally, these photometers are installed pointing at the zenith. However, as emphasised by [23], this is not optimal for total-emission monitoring; ideally, photometers should be installed 1 km from the settlement being monitored, pointing directly at its centre.

Pollution **measurement tools must guarantee that rising readings reflect real increases in pollution.** Instruments whose metrics can decrease despite growing pollution are unreliable for widespread use by non-expert personnel, even if they remain valuable in expert-controlled settings. Issues such as strong ageing effects[47], lack of spectral

³ <https://pmisson.users.earthengine.app/view/sdgsat-eu-visual>

sensitivity, or high dependency on the photometer's location should disqualify a photometer from use by non-experts. **Ground monitoring is essential** to compensate for some of the deficiencies of satellite data, such as a lack of intra-night sensitivity, a lack of spectral discrimination[48], a lack of sensitivity to horizontal lighting[24], [33], [34], and limited spatial resolution[24], [33]. Except for horizontal light detection, these **limitations** can be partially **addressed by combining different satellite capabilities**, but never with the precision that even low-cost ground-based devices can provide[49]. Conversely, it is impossible to achieve the same geographic coverage with ground-based instruments. **Both techniques are essential.** What matters is being aware of each one's limitations.

This guide is intended to advise on how to measure total light pollution emissions from large sources and their variations, not natural variations in sky brightness due to the Moon, aerosols, airglow, auroras, or other atmospheric phenomena. Its focus is on monitoring near pollution sources to minimise the influence of such natural effects and ensure reliable measurements. Many of these photometers are still ideal for monitoring natural sky brightness variations, as sky brightness should be treated as a meteorological variable that depends on both natural and artificial components[50], [51]. This should not be confused with monitoring total ground-based ALAN for applications by non-experts, who need to report on compliance with environmental standards.

Photometer Comparison

Below is a **list of photometers available on the market**. The authors were unable to obtain technical information for all devices despite contacting various manufacturers. It should also be noted that, in general, the listed photometers are not traceably calibrated or built to scientific standards that allow **easy conversion to radiometric units**. However, there are no major technical barriers to achieving this; the **current issue is primarily a lack of user demand and awareness**. [13] details how to convert steradian-based magnitudes commonly used by these devices into radiometric units. Other authors, such as Salvador Bará, have conducted related work.

Photometric Networks

- REECL (SQM), (ES)
- Stars4All (TESS-W and TESS-4C), Global
- BuioMetria Partecipativa (IT) (Decommissioned)
- SQM ARPA Veneto network (IT)
- Globe at Night / Loss of the Night (SQM), Global
- MeteoGalicía, SQM (Galicia, ES)
- EELabs (Corvo Island (PT), Madeira (PT), La Palma (ES), Gran Canaria (ES), Tenerife (ES), Badajoz (ES))
- IAA-CSIC, SQMs with Filters and TESS-W and TESS-4C (Andalusia, ES)

- Upper Austrian SQM network (AT)
- Austrian Network of Lightmeters (AT)
- Lightmeter Network (AT)
- La Réunion (FR)
- Measurement Network Rhön (TESS-W) (DE), himmelsmonitoring.de
- Netherlands (NL)/NW-Germany, SQM (DE), <https://www.washetdonker.nl/>

4.4.3 Cameras

One of the main advantages of cameras is **their high spatial resolution**. This allows not only the **measurement of sky brightness or direct/reflected emissions at a single point**, but also **across multiple points simultaneously**. Moreover, calibrated cameras are already available on the market for various applications. However, apart from networks like *FRIPON* or *AstMon*, it is uncommon for these cameras to be permanently installed. An interesting capability is the calibration of these devices using standard stars, enabling absolute calibration[52] if atmospheric extinction is corrected. A catalogue prepared specifically for this purpose is available[53]. There appear to be no significant technical barriers to the widespread adoption of these devices, aside from cost: photometers typically range from €200 to €1,000, whereas cameras range from €500 to €20,000.

4.4.4 Inventory of Light Sources

The usefulness of an inventory depends on its level of detail and the ease with which the data can be linked to both radiance measurements and propagation models. In light of the parameters in the tool described by [54], it is recommended that **each luminaire** include the metadata listed below.

These data are recommended for individual streetlight records. For effective light-pollution control, however, it is not strictly necessary to reach this level of detail. The **sufficient parameters are**:

- Number of fixtures per model.
- Power per lamp.
- Upward hemispheric flux.
- Operating hours per power level.
- Correlated color temperature.
- Luminous efficacy.
- Environment type (rural or urban).

Moreover, many light-pollution sources beyond public lighting, such as ornamental or commercial lighting, private fixtures, security lights, windows, and vehicles-are difficult to inventory. [35] showed that satellite imagery can outperform traditional inventories by

including private lighting. Citizen-science methodologies can also help maintain and update inventories for aspects that are not easily catalogued[34], [49]. In any case, inventories complement other tools but remain a fundamental instrument for the responsible public management of light pollution.

Recommended Metadata at the Luminaire Level

1. Identification and Location

- Unique identifier (UUID).
- Coordinates (lat, lon) in WGS84, precision 1 m.
- Mounting height (m) and support type (pole, facade, mast, etc.).

2. Photometric Characteristics

- Nominal luminous flux (lm) and luminous efficacy (lm W⁻¹).
- Photometric distribution: IES/LDT file or candela-angle matrix.
- Upward Light Output Ratio (ULOR, %).
- Maintenance factor (L_x, %).

3. Spectral Characteristics

- Correlated color temperature (CCT, K).
- RGB spectral breakdown.

4. Power and Consumption

- Electrical power of the system (W). The time of use-typically 4100–4300 h per year-can be used to estimate energy consumption.
- Estimated annual energy use (kWh year⁻¹).

5. Schedule and Control

- Operating schedule (hours per day, days per year).
- Control strategy (dimming, part-night switch-off, presence detection, IoT).

6. Maintenance History

- Installation date and last service date.
- Nominal lifespan of lamp, ballast, and fixture (hours or years).

7. Environmental Context

- Setting classification (rural, suburban, urban, industrial, natural), or at least whether the lamps are higher than the surrounding buildings.
- Proximity to sensitive areas (astronomical reserves, Special Protection Areas [SPAs], parks, observatories, nesting areas, rivers, etc.).
- Distance between buildings.

8. Ownership and Traceability

- Owner or managing entity.
- Data source (in situ survey, cadastre, estimate) and uncertainty (%).

Recommended Database Structure

- Use GeoPackage (.gpkg) or a PostGIS database with a normalized schema.
- Include lookup tables for photometric models (IES/LDT) and lamp spectra.
- Implement version control via git-lfs or an equivalent system (with “production” and “development” branches).

Linking with Models and Measurements

- Street-level photometric measurements.
- Audit records.

Governance and Access

- Appoint a data manager and formalize automatic backups.
- Publish non-sensitive fields under a CC-BY 4.0 license where permitted by law.
- Include clauses in lighting contracts to ensure that providers deliver records in the standard format.
- The format should be compatible with OpenStreetMap when possible.

4.4.5 Other Solutions

- LanCube

The LanCube is a cube-shaped device designed to measure ALAN in multiple directions and spectral bands (Red, Green, Blue, and Clear). It captures data using sensors on each face and calculates indices like the *Melatonin Suppression Index*, *Star Light Index*, and *Induced Photosynthesis Index* to **assess the impact of light on health, ecosystems, and the night sky**. Portable and efficient, it can be mounted on a car to map urban lighting quickly and in high detail, although it is not sensitive enough to measure sky brightness.

It can be used as a potential tool for model validation[55].

- SAND

The *Spectrophotometer for Aerosol Night Detection* (SAND) is a scientific instrument developed by Prof. Martin Aubé to monitor aerosol optical properties during nighttime. By analyzing artificial skyglow, SAND provides valuable data on light pollution and atmospheric aerosols. The latest version, SAND-4, employs a long-slit spectrometer coupled with a cooled CCD camera to capture high-resolution spectra of the night sky. This setup enables researchers to assess the impact of artificial lighting on the environment and to retrieve aerosol optical depth measurements at night. SAND has been deployed in various locations, including the Universidad Complutense de Madrid and

ARPA Veneto in Padua (Italy), where it continuously records spectral data to study urban light pollution and its interactions with atmospheric conditions[56].

4.5 Summary of Advantages and Limitations of Each Method

Satellites are the easiest-and often the only-way to obtain information on the largest spatial scales. However, it is important to understand the limitations of each platform. As demonstrated in case studies, the most effective approach is to combine data from different satellites, ideally ISS, SDGSAT-1, and VIIRS.

When the signal is low, as in rural areas, other techniques-such as photometry-are often more sensitive.

In general, **photometers** are not used optimally to track the evolution of light emissions, as they are typically pointed toward the zenith and located far from the emission sources. Additionally, most photometers are too simple to be used by non-experts in a way that produces easily interpretable results. This can be addressed by using appropriate filters, avoiding devices with significant aging effects, and aiming them directly at the target light source from approximately 1 km. A major advantage of photometers is their high temporal resolution.

Cameras offer higher spatial and spectral resolution than typical photometers. The main limitation is their high cost, which makes it difficult to achieve dense spatial coverage.

Advantages

- Large spatial coverage (**satellites**).
- High temporal resolution (**photometers**).
- High spatial and spectral resolution (**cameras**).

Limitations

- Limited sensitivity in rural areas (**satellites**).
- Logistical maintenance requirements (**photometers**).
- High cost and limited spatial coverage (**cameras**).

The total-light-emission metric is fundamental for addressing light-pollution challenges. Its proper implementation requires integrating calibrated satellite sensors, detailed source inventories, rigorous physical corrections, and a multi-scale analysis strategy. Combining photometers, calibrated cameras, and orbital data provides a robust framework for evaluating and managing artificial nighttime light.

4.6 Open Access and Licensing Considerations

As already stated explicitly in the Grant Agreement, not all data and software produced in PLAN-B can be made fully open access due to third-party licensing constraints. Specifically:

- **SDGSAT-1 data:** The original data are distributed under a **non-commercial** license and cannot be redistributed by PLAN-B. Access to the raw products must be formally requested from the **International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals**⁴.
- **Google Earth Engine (GEE):** Part of the processing relies on GEE, which is explicitly authorized **only for research** use and not for operational or commercial purposes.
- **ISS imagery:** Astronaut photographs from the ISS can be made **fully open access**, and both individual images and mosaics generated in PLAN-B are being uploaded to open repositories.
- **Code and software:** The processing of ISS imagery combines both **new pipelines developed within PLAN-B** and **pre-existing proprietary software**. The PLAN-B components (e.g. automated georeferencing modules) will be released as open source, while the proprietary parts that predate the project cannot be shared.

Accordingly, and in line with what was agreed with the EC in the Grant Agreement, PLAN-B will:

1. Provide **access for bona fide researchers upon request** to restricted data under the existing licensing conditions.
2. Release **secondary open products** (e.g. derived indices, aggregated rasters, methodological documentation, scientific publications, and the open-source modules developed in PLAN-B) **to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and reusability**.

This approach fulfils Horizon Europe open science requirements while respecting third-party licenses, exactly as foreseen in the Grant Agreement.

4.7 Relevance for the Policy Brief

The **high-resolution exposure maps** (SDGSAT-1) and the automated georeferencing of ISS imagery produced under *Task 2.1* directly support the strategic directions outlined in the [PLAN-B Policy Brief “Restoring the Night”](#) [3]. By providing harmonised, spatially detailed,

⁴ <https://www.cbac.ac.cn/en/>

and spectrally rich information on artificial light emissions, these datasets **address two of the Brief's core priorities**:

1. Establishing a **coherent monitoring framework** to quantify light pollution across **Europe**, and
2. **Enabling biodiversity-relevant assessments** through metrics of ecological connectivity and nocturnal landscape quality.

In particular, the SDGSAT-1 colour map of Europe and the georeferenced ISS composites underpin the recommendation **to integrate light pollution into EU environmental protection frameworks by supplying the evidence base for policy**, from Natura 2000 site management to national biodiversity strategies. These products also exemplify the Policy Brief's call for openness and transparency of monitoring data, while recognising that licensing restrictions necessitate controlled access to certain raw datasets.

5 Ecological Connectivity and Protection of the Nocturnal Landscape Against Light Pollution

5.1 The Need for Effective Connectivity Between Protected Areas

Territorial fragmentation induced by urban growth, infrastructure, and especially the expansion of **artificial lighting poses a serious threat to nocturnal biodiversity**. **Most wildlife species rely on natural cycles of light and dark** for reproduction, orientation, migration, and survival. In fact, over **70% of species** exhibit predominantly **nocturnal** behaviours, and it is estimated that **at least 51% of threatened species are sensitive to the effects of light pollution**.

Light pollution acts as an invisible but effective barrier that **disrupts ecological corridors**[15] and **limits movement between habitats**. To address this phenomenon, it is essential to **ensure connectivity between protected areas**, such as those in the Natura 2000 Network, by:

- Strictly limiting artificial lighting within and around protected areas.
- Establishing *dark ecological corridors* that facilitate the safe transit of nocturnal species[57].
- Incorporating light as a key variable in environmental impact and strategic assessment studies.

5.1.1 Tools for Developing Connectivity Maps

The tools used are like those employed in estimating total light pollution emissions, with some nuances. Note that the spatial resolution of satellite imagery may limit the ability to identify potential dark corridors within populated areas, where a resolution of a few meters may be necessary to determine urban connectivity [58].

On the other hand, inventories can be very helpful when sufficiently high-resolution satellite images are unavailable, but they must be supported by modelling efforts [59]. Drones, balloons, or even aircraft can be highly effective for this application [24], [60], [61], [62].

Fixed photometers are of limited use in this context, but they can be valuable when mounted on vehicles to analyze the diffuse glow of ALAN and the extent of illuminated areas, as demonstrated in [63].

5.2 Biological and Ecological impact

At the **physiological level**, artificial light has effects such as disruption of circadian rhythms, changes in immune responses, and alterations in hormone production [64], [65]. Circadian rhythms are endogenous mechanisms that enable animals to anticipate and adapt to daily environmental cycles, and they are closely linked to other vital processes such as feeding, reproduction, and responses to predation risk [66]. Given that ALAN became widespread, the **effects on wildlife became a common environmental issue** [67]. For instance, the hormone melatonin, which stabilises circadian rhythms, has synthesis inhibited by light and is widely studied in the context of artificial light pollution. These effects of ALAN on wildlife are well described for diverse groups such as insects [68], and vertebrates [64], [67], [69].

At the **ecological level**, ALAN is increasingly recognised as a driver of behavioural change across species, with cascading consequences for ecological processes. By altering natural diel cycles, ALAN interferes with activities that are tightly coupled to light and dark cues, including foraging, reproduction, communication, and other behaviours [70], [71]. For instance, illumination can enhance the hunting success of visually oriented predators such as bats, owls, and spiders, while simultaneously increasing the predation risk for prey species that rely on darkness as a refuge [72]. Pollination is also threatened by ALAN, as many nocturnal pollinators are affected by artificial lights, disrupting nocturnal pollination networks that are not replaced by diurnal communities [73], [74]. This disruption not only diminishes plant reproductive success but may also cascade to other species, weakening ecosystem resilience.

ALAN is known to affect animal orientation [71]. Migratory species are particularly vulnerable, facing increased risk of disorientation and mortality due to light attraction [75]. Migrating animals can perceive distant skyglow, which strongly influences their flight paths [76]. It is therefore critical to understand how artificial light and the degradation of the nocturnal landscape create barriers within ecological corridors.

Over time, such physiological stress can affect survival, recruitment, and ultimately species composition. Sensitive or specialist species tend to decline, while light-tolerant or generalist taxa expand their ranges, leading to biotic homogenization [77]. As trophic interactions are modified, trophic cascades may arise, with changes at one trophic level propagating through entire communities.

5.2.1 Nocturnal ecological connectivity

ALAN alters individual behaviour and disrupts the spatial and temporal connectivity of nocturnal ecosystems. This connectivity is essential for key processes like dispersal and genetic exchange, though the full scope of these nocturnal dynamics lacks a comprehensive synthesis in scientific literature [70]. Many species depend on natural darkness to move between habitats (i.e., feeding, reproduction, or migration), and the widespread increase of ALAN creates a mosaic of “bright” and “dark” patches that act as barriers or filters. For instance, light sources drive nocturnal pollinators away from their natural foraging routes, leading to reduced connectivity and declines in plant reproductive success [73]. For amphibians and reptiles, which often rely on darkness for orientation and predator avoidance, illuminated areas can function as hostile habitats, obstructing movement between breeding and feeding sites [78]. Therefore, fragmentation of the nocturnal environment can reduce access to resources, limit dispersal, and ultimately constrain species’ ranges [70], [71], [79].

The disruption of nocturnal connectivity has broader implications for ecosystem resilience. By reducing the permeability of landscapes at night, ALAN contributes to habitat fragmentation and biotic homogenization, often favouring light-tolerant or generalist species at the expense of specialists [80]. Such shifts can restructure communities and alter ecosystem services, from pollination to pest regulation, reinforcing the importance of darkness as an ecological resource [81].

6 The Nocturnal Landscape as a Common Good and Cultural Heritage

6.1 The Need to Protect the Nocturnal Landscape

At a given moment, **50% of the Earth is experiencing night**. This means that **every ecosystem has a nocturnal component**. The alteration of the nocturnal landscape can have a dramatic effect, including large-scale phenomenological changes [82], disruptions to the predator-prey dynamics, and interference with migratory routes, among other environmental impacts [83].

However, natural landscapes at night are **not only an ecological resource**, but they are also a **fundamental element of our cultural and scientific heritage**[84], [85], [86]. Natural night has shaped worldviews, navigation, spirituality, science and art in numerous civilisations for millennia. Preserving this landscape is tantamount to safeguarding an essential part of humanity's intangible legacy.

This vision was enshrined in the **La Palma Declaration of 2007**, also known as the *Declaration in Defense of the Night Sky and the Right to Starlight*. This initiative recognizes that:

”The starry sky, in addition to being a resource for science, is a heritage of humanity and a right of future generations. Its contemplation has influenced many cultures and civilisations and has inspired reflection and knowledge since time immemorial.”

In this sense, **light pollution represents a form of cultural and environmental loss to the extent that it can even produce cultural genocides** [87]. Its expansion reduces access to dark skies, undermines territorial identity, and harms scientific activities such as astronomy or nighttime environmental monitoring by remote sensing.

The quality of the **nightscape is increasingly recognised as a vital ecological resource**. **Darkness** is not simply the lack of light; it is a **fundamental habitat** dimension that structures the activity patterns, physiology, and ecological interactions of nocturnal and crepuscular species [70], [81]. **Preserving nightscape** quality is thus **critical for biodiversity conservation**, as it **maintains the temporal niche separation** that underpins species coexistence and the integrity of ecological processes. From an ecological perspective, degradation of the nightscape through skyglow, direct glare, or scattered **light alters the sensory environment** in ways comparable to habitat loss or fragmentation [70], [71]. Species adapted to darkness experience physiological stress and behavioural changes

that reduce fitness and survival [88]. Beyond individual species, the **nightscape provides landscape-scale ecological functions**. Natural darkness sustains ecological connectivity at night, facilitates migration and dispersal, and supports the functioning of ecosystems that rely on diel and seasonal cycles. Acknowledging darkness as a finite ecological resource is essential to ensure that biodiversity is protected from pollutants such as artificial light [81], [89].

6.1.1 Tools for Creating Nocturnal Landscape Maps

As with total-emission estimates and connectivity mapping, the same tools are useful here, albeit to varying degrees. For landscape monitoring, cameras are essential because they can directly capture two-dimensional brightness patterns. Photometers are useful for continuous monitoring, but although zenith sky brightness provides insight into the degree of impact, it is of limited ecological interest. Some photometers, such as the *TESS-Autoscan*, can capture information across the entire celestial sphere. Satellite imagery, while not providing sky-brightness maps directly, can be used with models-such as those in [90]-to generate them.

An example is the work carried out for over 10 years by the U.S. National Park Service [91]. In Europe, pioneering studies have been conducted by researchers and activists such as Joanma Bullón[92], Andreas Jechow[93], Andreas Hänel, and the *NIXNOX project*[94].

A highly relevant publication is [95], which should be updated to include the latest photometers and cameras. Several tools are currently being developed in this area, such as *AZOTEA*[96] and *DigiCaLum* by Zoltán Kolláth *et al.*

The main issue is not a lack of techniques for monitoring or modelling the night sky, but rather the lack of their systematic application and long-term maintenance.

7 Strategic Recommendations

Based on the shared diagnosis in the *Granada Manifesto on Light Pollution (2023)*[2], the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Regulatory recognition of the night sky as an environmental and cultural resource.
2. Inclusion of artificial light as an environmental pollutant in European and national legislation.
3. Integration of the nocturnal landscape into environmental impact and planning instruments.
4. Development of a nocturnal ecological connectivity framework.
5. Promotion of green and blue infrastructure integrated with “dark” infrastructure.

6. Support for establishing protected dark-sky zones.
7. Encouragement of citizen participation and open access to lighting data.
8. Promotion of awareness campaigns on the importance of natural nocturnal environments.

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